

Managing Cultural Diversities in Internationalisation of Business

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1. INTRODUCTION

The trend of globalization has made the different culture walk onto a worldwide stage (Marcelo and Deslree, 2004). In the business world, culture is treated as an important contribution to success

The trend of globalization accelerates the occurrence of international trades. More business opportunities and profits are waiting to be discovered in other countries. Better understanding and acceptance of different cultures can lead to more effective communication and, ultimately, more success.

With globalization it has become important to consider the impact of cultural differences when managing a team. Le Theuff (2005) argued that despite the globalization of the employment market there is no global employee as a result of culture. Intercultural management is a real concept adopted by companies as with globalization companies have to work with other companies all over the world. Any company who would not consider the multicultural dimension of his workforce might lead teams' projects to failure (Hofstede, 1993).

While the subject of cultural diversity and intercultural management is quite recent; so far only two explorative studies have been conducted as recently as the late 1990's. Up to this time there has been no evidence of a published explorative study within Indian multinationals implemented in South Korea. Only statistics have shown the patchwork of the cultural landscape in Indian's workforce.

Multinational companies in their aim to increase profitability and seek for solutions to problems related with the saturation of existing markets, often make an

effort to expand their operations to overseas markets. When a company decides to begin marketing products abroad, it will chose which fundamental strategic would be used: a standardized marketing mix (product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence, process management) and a single marketing strategy in all countries or whether to adjust itself and the marketing mix in other to fit to each local market (Vrontis & Thrassou, 2007). Business organizations may expand operations to foreign countries by setting up replicas (of part of) their value chains in those countries. Well-known examples of such organizations that use this strategy could be listed as Mc Donald's, The Body Shop and TATA Motors. The replication of a fixed format is associated with benefits, such as economies of scale and brand recognition (Winter & Szulanski, 2001) as cited in Jonsson & Foss (2011). In the international marketing, this is called the standardized marketing mix. Birnik & Bowman, (2007) mentioned about the advantages of this marketing strategy as following "Levitt (1983) has argued strongly for the globalization of markets based on technological drivers. Levitt's prescribed strategy is based on standardized products that will both take advantage of, and further reinforce increasingly homogeneous customer preferences on a global scale. Ohmae (1989) advocates a similar contingency solution when he concludes that the quest for universal product is not a generalizable prescription but that Levitt's prescribed global standardization makes perfect sense for certain segments and certain product categories." Therefore, standardized marketing mix strategy allowed the company to use the same brand name and same slogan for the same product all over the world. This strategy delivers an advantage which is cost saving. Since a standardized production

system is used across all business units, the company can use large economies of scale, which leads to the lower price of products to consumer, and then they can make their money with smaller margins spread across high numbers of consumers.

Tata Motors Limited, a USD 42 billion organisation, is a leading global automobile manufacturer with a portfolio that covers a wide range of cars, sports vehicles, buses, trucks and defence vehicles. The company's marque can be found on and off-road in over 175 countries around the globe.

Tata Motors Ltd is India's largest automobile company. The company is the leader in commercial vehicles in each segment, and among the top three in passenger vehicles with winning products in the compact, midsize car and utility vehicle segments. They are the world's fourth largest truck manufacturer, and the world's second largest bus manufacturer.

The company is engaged in the development, designing, manufacturing, assembling and sale of vehicles, including financing thereof, as well as sale of related parts and accessories. They manufacture commercial vehicle, three passenger vehicle, truck and bus. They have a portfolio of automotive products, ranging from sub-1 ton to 49 ton gross vehicle weight (GVW), trucks (including pickup trucks) and from small, medium, and large buses and coaches to passenger cars, including the car, the Tata Nano.

The company's segments include automotive, and others, which include information technology (IT) services, construction equipment manufacturing, machine tools and factory automation solutions, high-precision tooling and plastic and electronic components for certain applications, and investment business.

The company is rapidly increasing its global footprint and is aiming to match the standards of international automobile manufacturers in next 3 to 5 years. This rise to the level of a world-class automotive manufacturer would involve a large quantifiable increase in revenues from outside India with a focus on certain foreign markets. Currently international business contributes 18.4% to company's revenues. Company is aiming to increase it by 200% in near future to reduce its dependence on one single economy and one single business cycle.

Acquisitions are a crucial component of the global expansion of Tata enterprises. Over the past eight years the group has made overseas acquisitions of \$18

billion. Among the bigger deals on this front have been Tetley, Brunner Mond, Corus, Jaguar and Land Rover in the UK, Daewoo Commercial Vehicles in South Korea, NatSteel in Singapore, and Tyco Global Network and General Chemical in the US.

Therefore, this research will be focused on one of the major international ventures of TATA Motors in recent past, i.e. Daewoo Commercial Vehicle Company of South Korea.

1.1 Research Background

Cultural diversity is a growing phenomenon that has increased attention and importance in the 21st century. There are major facts and trends that maneuver this in the beginning of this century, the first being the globalization of economies with rise of Asia, where in the next 30 years 50 percent of the worlds' GDP is expected to be represented; the second trend is the involvement of international teams as a key driving force of innovations; the third being the critical concerns of this century such as global warming, pandemic diseases, terrorism and weapons which has a global effect; finally the fourth being the changes in demographics via globalization and international trade accelerated international migration and diversity across borders (Stewart, 2007). One of the critical impacts of migration and globalization is the "dramatic increase in the opportunity and need to interact with people" who are diverse in culture (Thomas & Inkson, 2009). Europe with its shift in workforce, economic and political changes within the European Union has paved way to highly mobile and diverse society living and working within the European economic area (Allwood et al., 2007). It's fast becoming a fact of life where intercultural interactions take place regardless of an individual's interest in acquaintance of another person from a culturally different background. In these instances the situation demands day to day interactions at work, social or in educational institutions (Allwood et al., 2007). Thus the thinking has changed on cultural diversity from being a "melting pot" to "multiculturalism", accepting it as an essential part of a society (Parvis, 2003). These inferences the fact that organizations will increasingly require internationally accomplished work force and it goes without saying that their ability to manage the cultural diversity plays a major role in their success in the future (Stewart, 2007; Parvis, 2003).

Establishments of institutions such as Cultural Diversity Consultants in 2003 and Multicultural

Centrum in the 1980s are other examples emphasizing the cultural integration and management of the differences in Sweden, where they are strategically creating programs and networks to integrate people beyond their cultural differences (Hamde, 2008). The cultural diversity is experienced and managed at individual, social and at professional level increasingly in this country. This has also increased the attention and discussions on diversity in general in Sweden (Fagerlind & Ekelov, 2001), especially within the organizational settings that unfolds and is also viewed as a strategic resource (Hamde, 2008). Further an organization is an arena where “social construction of diversity uncovers the interaction between the various elements and mechanisms of working life which transcends traditional borders between labour market, work environment and work organization” (De loss Reyes, 2001).

Expansion and intense globalization requires not just countries’ but also organizations’ capability to be more open and accommodative to a heterogeneous working environment. It needs to be noticed that regardless of whether it’s international or domestic, cultural diversity does influence how organization perform (Adler, 1997). Thus globalization of trade and culture in combination with the increasingly expanding diverse domestic workforce is an effective skill set to excel in organizational performance. An organization that effectively manages its cultural diversity succeeds with the well- deserved competitive edge while others lack (Stevens & Ogunji, 2011). Differences in people’s values, attitudes and behaviour that are grounded from diverse culture influence how managerial events are viewed in an organization (Adler, 1997). Still it needs to be asked whether the organizations take note of these differences in culture and benefit from it. Managing the diverse cultures in an organization plays an essential role in achieving competitive edge in its market (Kundu, 2001). This emphasizes on the importance of a firm’s ability to deal and absorb the benefits from cultural diversity towards the wealth of the organization which is a key requirement for survival not just at a domestic level but even in the international settings. Thus “to manage effectively in a global or a domestic multicultural environment, we need to recognize the differences and learn to use them to our advantage, rather than either attempting to ignore them or simply allowing them to cause problems” (Adler, 1997). Hence managing the cultural diversity constructively in a firm is of growing concern.

1.2 Problem Statement

The story about TATA Motors's successful development, particular organizational capacities, and the bold and inspired leadership of its entrepreneur-founder have been largely written up and commented. Its organization, communication, marketing, product range, and even store layouts, all tell us the same story- the story of the "TATA Motors Way." Indeed, the "TATA Motors Way" that facilitates its successful international expansion is the combination of vision, characteristic leadership, sound business principle that subtly reinforced by the influence of Indian culture.

Although the company has succeeded with their global strategy in the past in most of the markets it had entered, it quickly learnt that success in the Korean market required a different strategy in the areas of Marketing and HR (Kumar, 2005). The standardized strategy which is adopted by TATA Motors could lead to some disadvantages because following this strategy, Indian managers are sent to other branches in the world in other to ensure the TATA Motors way is implemented in the local areas. Thus, the conflict between the Indian management and local employees could occur due to the cultural differences. Especially in the country like South Korea where the traditional cultures and values are dignified, Korean employees have been programmed in their mind for long a working culture differs from the Indian way that TATA Motors wants to influence to their employees, problems were unavoidable. When TATA Motors were keen to increase revenue in Asian markets like South Korea, they faced the challenge to manage their staffs from the conflicts and the diversity of Korean cultures, such as how to train people within TATA Motors perform in a standardized format to keep its essential value, and how to avoid the misunderstanding while improve employee performance. Recognizing and understanding the importance of cross cultural management between India and South Korea, TATA Motors managers definitely have been spending time, energy and effort to understand the differences of national, corporate and functional cultures before starting on setting up the strategic plans.

Operating in a country with the culture base different from the corporate culture could bring many challenges to MNE. Survey entitled “What is the biggest barrier in doing business in the world market” figured out eight problems which include “law, price competition, information, language, delivery, foreign currency, time differences, and cultural differences”. Thus,

international companies when entering South Korea have faced the great barriers caused by cultural differences such as difficulty of communication, higher potential transaction costs, different objectives and means of cooperation and operating methods. These problems have led to the failure of many Sino-foreign cooperation projects. Therefore, questions concerning how to do business in South Korea such as “how to understand South Korea” and “how to do business with Korean people” have been raised in the strategy of companies want to enter South Korea (Zhang, 2004) Coming to South Korea in 1998, TATA Motors has been provided cheap labour, abundant resources and the potential business market. However, TATA Motors faced challenges of bureaucracy system, high duty rates and customer’s behaviour (Chaletanone, Cheancharadpong, 2008).

1.3 Aims and Objectives

It could be established from the previous discussion that a study on cultural diversity in an organizational scenario and how it is managed within, is of importance at this point of time. Thus the aim of this study is to investigate how organizations in South Korea today manage cultural diversity. The researcher intends to do this through investigating TATA Motors and how they view the subject of cultural diversity.

Objectives of the research are:

- To understand the concept of cultural diversities in internationalization of business
- To describe and analyze the managerial practices of TATA Motors in South Korea under the influence of Korean business culture
- To figure out the flexibility in the strategy of the company in the effort of retaining the standardized structure but still be able to adapt to the culture different from its background.
- To give recommendations for TATA Motors how to manage cultural diversity and be prepared to utilize this growing trend of a diverse cultural market.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs, and backgrounds than ever before. People no longer live and work in an insular marketplace; they are now part of a worldwide economy with competition coming from nearly every continent. For this reason,

organizations need diversity to become more creative and open to change. Therefore maximizing and capitalizing on workplace diversity has become an important issue for management today. Since managing diversity remains a significant organizational challenge, managers must learn the managerial skills needed in a multicultural work environment. Supervisors and managers must be prepared to teach themselves and others within their organizations to value multicultural differences in both associates and customers so that everyone is treated with dignity.

Diversity issues are now considered important and are projected to become even more important in the future due to increasing differences in the population of many countries. Companies need to focus on diversity and look for ways to become totally inclusive organizations because diversity has the potential of yielding greater productivity and competitive advantages. Managing and valuing diversity is a key component of effective people management, which can improve workplace productivity. Unmanaged diversity in the workplace might become an obstacle for achieving organizational goals. Therefore diversity can be perceived as a “double-edged sword”.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Culture

There are many ways to define culture and it differs from authors to authors. According to Ferraro (1994) culture is “everything that people have, think and do as members of their society”. Philips (1994) shares the same view as Ferraro adding that culture is a set of shared suppositions by a group of persons. These suppositions are implicit guides for thoughts, feelings and behaviours which are representatives of the values and standards of the group.

2.1.1 National culture

Hofstede (1991) defines the national culture as the set of rules which determines the actions and thoughts of a given group. It relates to the common languages, religion, politics, and morals and so on. This culture evolves with the country’s history, in this same regard Iribarne (1998) explains that past events determines the way a country installs its institutions such as the one for education, politics and financials.

2.1.2 Cultural differences

The world is moving closer to a global economy however it is important not to lose focus of cultural factors. One way of gaining cultural understanding is to examine different cultural elements within a team. Understanding cultural differences is important to achieve success in projects and team work.

2.2 Hofstede's View

Hofstede (1993) conducted a survey in over 50 countries, within the same multinational group (IBM), which revealed common problems within four areas. His aim was to measure and understand cultural differences impacting the management of multinationals:

- Power distance
- Individualism and collectivism
- Male and female
- Uncertainty avoidance

2.3 Trompenaars's View

Trompenaars (1996) completed Hofstede's research; he conducted a survey among 30 different companies over 50 countries. From his research he identified seven dimensions of culture:

- Individualism and collectivism
- Universalism and particularism
- Specific and diffuse culture
- Neutral and emotional relationships
- Achievement and ascription
- Sequential and synchronic
- Internal and external control

2.4 Cateora & Ghauri's View

Authors such as Cateora & Ghauri (2000) give to culture five main elements which are: Material culture, Social institutions, Aesthetics, Belief system, Education and Language. They acknowledge that each of these cultural elements should be evaluated in terms of how it could affect strategic management within a multinational. A company should take into consideration the material culture of a country where its economy, its infrastructure should be regarded. The social institutions should be studied in terms of the role of men & women within the community, for example in many countries the role of the woman is to stay at home while the man will be the provider of the family.

2.5 Cultural Diversity

Cultural diversity is further categorized as a primary dimension based on the different definitions of culture that is found. From these different definitions the authors state their own definition of cultural diversity and national culture that will be followed throughout this paper. In connection to this, how cultural diversity could affect organizations will be presented in terms of how it can be beneficial in certain situations and problematic in other, both in terms of difficulties but also through conflicts. This part ends with discussing organizational culture in relation to cultural diversity.

2.6 Discussion on Cultural Diversity

In understanding the concept of cultural diversity the authors start the discussion by defining what culture is. Since culture is a popular subject there are many definitions of culture which represent the complexity of the phenomena and it can, in the same way as in the explanation of diversity, be seen many wide definitions of the concept.

According to Varner and Beamer (2011) "Culture explains how people make sense of their world" (Varner & Beamer, 2011). It could be said that any individual will be submitted to a natural part of a learning process from their early childhood which forms the basis as to how everything is interpreted. Hence it could be stated that culture can be described as the way of life of a group of people (Seymen, 2006) and that is shared by all or almost all members of some social group (Seymen, 2006). This definition is much in line with Geert Hofstede's view on culture. He is a popular anthropologist and sees culture as the "software of the mind" that separates members of different groups from each other (Hofstede, 1991). This software, or mental programming, is based on the social environments where people grew up and developed their life experiences (Hofstede, 1991). To further narrow down what culture is and where it comes from, Kluckhohn and Kroeber said that "the essential core of culture consists of traditional (i.e. historically derived and selected) ideas and especially their attached values" (Kluckhohn & Kroeber, 1952). This is in turn passed on from one generation to the next (Samovar et al., 2009). Furthermore, culture consists of explicit and implicit patterns (Kluckhohn, 1951) and includes customs, morals and laws that shapes behaviour and affects how the world is viewed (Adler, 1997).

2.7 Cultures in Organizations

Cultural diversity is very important to organizations that have adopted global strategies (Adler, 1997). When doing business internationally or with multicultural teams it is important to understand other cultures and, as stated in the beginning of this paper, that this is a growing issue today. Organizations' interest in understanding cultural diversity can be depending on the organizational culture.

Organizational culture is an abstract concept with many different definitions (Barney, 1986). It is however often explained as "a complex set of values, beliefs, assumptions, and symbols that define the way in which a firm conducts its business" (Barney, 1986). This explanation has many similarities to the concept of culture as described earlier. Hofstede explains organizational culture as "the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one organization from another" (Hofstede, 1991) which is much like his definition of culture but here in a collective form. This shows that culture has many similarities with organizational culture which can indicate that an organization's culture can affect the company in many ways, just as an individual's culture affects the person through for example behaviour and morals. Every social unit that has a shared history have developed a culture (Schein, 2010) which develops as a group of people tries to cope with their surroundings (Trice & Beyer, 1993).

2.8 Managing Cultural Diversity

Globalization and international presence of an organization fuelled by various operational motivations has implications on performance and the management of broad cultural diversity (Palich & Gomez-Mejia, 1999). This emphasizes the fact that cultural diversity is becoming an increasingly common phenomenon (Appelbaum et al., 1998). It is indeed a crucial challenge of this century and a concern for domestic as well as the international organizations to manage the difference in culture effectively (Palich & Gomez-Mejia, 1999). Green et al. states that "managing diversity involves a departure from collective views of groups of people to valuing individual differences and talent in the workplace" (Green et al. 2002), which also shows that this subject is more than simply recognizing the differences in humans and their values in an organization. Organizations that constitute of different cultures should build itself by acknowledging different values of the employees and incorporate it in all

dimensions of its system (Kundu, 2001). It is observed that if the concept of cultural diversity is intrinsic in an organization's value system the firms tend to create diversity friendly environment through the implementation of policies that integrates every member of the organization (McKay et al., 2009). Similarly such firms identify diversity as an asset and utilize towards the progress of the organization and the employees in meeting the needs of its end user (McKay et al., 2009).

As previously discussed different individual perceptions are affected by different cultural conditioning and people react differently to a situation than people from similar cultures, hence "cultural diversity breeds divergent reactions" (Adler, 1997; Punnett, 1995). According to Adler (2008), very few managers consider culture having any effects on the daily activities of an organization, let alone recognizing the difference in culture within its operational territory. This is often identified as the cultural blindness, which is the tendency to ignore the cultural differences or just not being aware of them (Kalyanpur, 1998). Cultural blindness is a common factor among most managers and organizations, although recognition of any cultural difference is also often considered primitive and rude (Adler and Gundersen, 2008). As Adler and Gundersen (2008) states, managers who recognize diversity are accused of being "prejudiced, racist and unprofessional" and they are being encouraged to view individuals only for their professional skills. Eventually it could be stated that cultural blindness often could be caused either by not seeing the difference at all or by them not being recognized due to negative connotations that it may have. Hence attention given to the cultural difference often has conflicting views and results. Similarly this may project, as people are being more alike than different and lead to "assuming, imagining, and actually perceiving similarity when differences exist" (Adler and Gundersen, 2008). Nevertheless this paradoxical disposition does create a dilemma in most organizations as to address the challenges of cultural blindness and manage it well enough to encompass it into its system. Neglecting or rejecting the cultural differences leads to unproductive working environment which restricts the firm from exploiting its untapped opportunities of its diverse cultural workforce (Adler and Gundersen, 2008). Still it needs to be emphasized that the identification of these differences also helps to exclude or reduce the conflicts that arise out of cultural diversity and exploit it in favour of the firm (Adler and Gundersen, 2008). Thus "to manage effectively in a global or a domestic multicultural environment, we

need to recognize the differences and learn to use them to our advantage, rather than either attempting to ignore them or simply allowing them to cause problems” (Adler, 1997).

The senior management hence should drive the process of the management of diversity as a “holistic institutional management strategy” (Gwele, 2009) to effectively manage cultural diversity. Gwele (2009) further stated that the “significance of strategically positioning diversity management as part of the institution's strategic direction cannot be overemphasized”. Therefore strategy plays a key role in assimilating and positioning diversity at a higher level of an organization's long term direction. Strategy is defined as the “direction and scope of an organization over the long term, which achieves advantage in a changing environment through its configuration of resource and competences with the aim of fulfilling stakeholder expectations, or simply a long term direction of an organization (Johnson et al., 2008). Chandler (1962) defines strategy as “determination of the basic long-term goals and objective of an enterprise, and the adoption of course of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying out these goals”. It could more simply be defined as a long term direction of an organization (Johnson et al., 2008). According to Johnson et al., (2008), “culture is, in effect, an unintended driver of strategy”. Clegg et al, (2011) stated that the “Strategic importance of cultures resides in their pervasive impact on how organizational members makes sense of opportunities and challenges, how they deal with problems and how they discuss them”. Culture is undoubtedly an influential but unseen powerful factor that has an impact on how the work force interprets the activities in its organizational environment.

If culture is an unintended driver of the strategy that actually defines the long term direction of an organization, as stated earlier, its influence most definitely needs to be identified and managed effectively. Johnson et al, (2008) further states that understanding cultural perspectives helps the firm to recognize its opportunities and restrictions that they face in forming their future strategy. Cultural diversity becomes more crucial as firms expand its “perspective, strategy, tactics or approach and try to reposition its strategy or organization” (Adler and Gundersen, 2008). Essentially these types process require firms to think out of the box and come up with new and innovative perspectives, away from their usual working practices. At the same time it is also necessary to incorporate

diversity at the strategic level to recognize and manage it accordingly to the extent that it is translated into action and viewed as a critical aspect of an organization. Hence a well- managed diversity creates and enhances synergy by increasing creativity, flexibility, solve complex problems, and improve company's reach towards its culturally different clienteles (Hayles, 1982). As a next step view and its influence on managing cultural diversity need to be evaluated to explore the effects it has on creating a synergistic environment within the organization.

There are numerous of conceptualizations of managing cultural diversity that exist in the literature. Presence of cultural diversity in an organization is seen as an increase of the level of creativity, in depth analysis of issues, improved decision making, flexibility, innovation along with diversity in point of view, approaches, and business practices (Adler & Gundersen, 2008; Stevens et. al., 2011; Cox & Blake, 1991). Diverse cultural origination is even seen as something that assures advantageous outcome in an organization (Williams & O'Reilly, 1998). However, cultural diversity also tends to create conflicts, miscommunication, misunderstanding, increased tension, and lack of cohesion, commitment has negative effects on the organization performance (Glick et. al., 1993, Adler and Gundersen, 2008). Hence the basic views differ in how organizations see the advantages and disadvantages of cultural diversity in their day to day operation. Similarly the views on cultural diversity and effective management of an organization's workforce are dispersed and make it difficult to find a common accepted method or a model cultural diversity management (Dadfar and Gustavsson, 1992). The dominant reason being the contrasting views taken by different authors on this topic, as some seem to consider the cultural diversity as beneficial and some view it as a source of problem which is hard to manage (Seymen, 2006). This obviously affects how cultural diversity is viewed upon and managed in organization.

3. Research Methodology

According to Patton (1984), there are two methodological approaches; the qualitative approach and the quantitative approach. Most qualitative approach said by the author that they allow the researcher to study selected issues in depth and detail. Furthermore, the data in this kind of approach is collected from fieldwork with the form of conversations and observations, instead of numbers.

Therefore, qualitative research gives the researchers advantages when collecting data since the obtained information would be richer and deeper. Therefore, with the research question concerning the cultural differences management of TATA Motors in South Korea regarding their staffs, qualitative research will fit well for the purpose of the paper. Since the research focuses on the management level, the authors needed to get valuable information by focusing on one certain type of area which is cultural differences at TATA Motors instead of wide-spreading information. There is a need of collecting relevant data, avoiding missing information, thus, in-depth interviews were conducted with selected managers whose works are connected to areas that the authors were going to investigate such as TATA Motors corporate culture, the TATA Motors Way, cultural differences management at TATA Motors and TATA Motors human resources management activities concerning recruitment and training; a set of questions were asked. Using qualitative method, the author will be able to encourage the participants express their views deeper and more detailed, the obtained information will be used to answer for the research question.

Furthermore, the deductive approach will be used in this paper, which was started by some previous researches concerning the standardized strategies regarding to TATA Motors marketing strategies in India, and South Korea.

As the authors mentioned above, the research approach will be more qualitative in nature, the best way to produce any suggestions about the research is to combine both the theories and the empirical findings. Thus, a descriptive approach will be adopted. The reason will be that under the geography, language and time frame limitation, the interviews conducted will be semi-structured, the topics, interviewees and questions to be asked were prepared in advance prior to the actual interview. The information collected during the interviews with different store managers of TATA Motors will provide a deep insight about many areas within the company, for example the historical background, the corporate culture as well as their programs in HR strategies. The authors will try to make the research coherent so that the empirical findings follow the structures of the theoretical framework, making it easier for the reader to comprehend the paper.

The source of data collection in order to write this research will be collected from both primary and secondary. Primary data obtained from interviews,

which is most common method to obtain data for business paper. Secondary data will also be used in which the author will review journals, articles, books, films and documents which will help him to analyze the information properly. The list of all articles, books and websites are given in the reference list. The interviews will be both made through phone and via email. Furthermore, the data analysis will be presented in terms of interview transcription and will be compared with the literature of the study in the discussion part in order to meet the desired research objectives.

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